

Call for papers

Advanced Medical Sciences: An International Journal (AMS) is a quarterly open access peer-reviewed journal that publishes articles which contribute new results in all areas of the Medical Sciences. The goal of this journal is to bring together researchers and practitioners from academia and industry to focus on understanding advances in Medical Sciences and establishing new collaborations in these areas.

Authors are solicited to contribute to the journal by submitting articles that illustrate research results, projects, surveying works and industrial experiences that describe significant advances in the areas of Medical Sciences.

Topics of interest include, but are not limited to, the following:

- Cardiovascular medicine and haematology
- Clinical sciences
- Complimentary and alternative medicine
- Dentistry
- Human movement and sports science
- Immunology
- Medical biochemistry and metabolomics
- Medical microbiology
- Medical physiology
- Neurosciences
- Nursing
- Nutrition and dietetics
- Oncology and carcinogenesis
- Optometry and ophthalmology
- Paediatrics and reproductive medicine
- Pharmacology and pharmaceutical sciences
- Public health and health services

Paper Submission

Authors are invited to submit papers for this journal through E-mail: ams_journal@airccse.com . Submissions must be original and should not have been published previously or be under consideration for publication while being evaluated for this Journal.

Important Dates

- **Submission Deadline : September 05, 2020**
- Notification : October 05, 2020
- Final Manuscript Due : October 13, 2020
- Publication Date : Determined by the Editor-in-Chief

For other details please visit <http://airccse.com/ams/index.html>